

ADVERSARIAL OPTIMIZATION SCHEME FOR ONLINE TRACKING MODEL ADAPTATION IN AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Online tracking model updating is typically addressed as a regression problem, involving the minimization of the dispersion between the obtained tracker model response maps in each consecutive frame and some target distribution (e.g., Gaussian), using a closed-form solution. Inspired by the recent applications of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), we propose to solve this problem with an adversarial optimization scheme, by employing a Generator-Discriminator network pair. That is, the role of the Generator is assigned to the tracking model so that it produces response maps belonging to some target distribution, while an additional discriminator network is trained to identify if the tracker response maps produced by the generator belong to this target distribution, or not. Therefore, the tracker model exploits the discriminator network as an additional information pool about the target distribution. It is shown that this simple addition improves tracking performance in standard benchmark datasets, without significantly hurting training complexity, thus rendering the proposed method suitable for embedded system application such as in autonomous cars and Unmanned Aerial Systems.

Index Terms— 2D visual target tracking, adversarial optimization scheme, autonomous systems

1. INTRODUCTION

2D visual tracking is perhaps one of the most heavily researched problems in the computer vision domain, due to its importance in real-time applications such as autonomous systems, robotics, media production, industrial semantic annotation, visual surveillance, human-computer interfaces and augmented reality. 2D visual tracking requires an input video stream and initial Region of Interest (ROI) depicting an object to be tracked, either by manual annotation or by an object detection algorithm, 2D visual tracking involves localizing this object in the successive video frames in the stream.

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Our applications of interest include embedded application in autonomous cars and Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), to be employed for autonomous car following and linear infrastructure inspection and maintenance, respectively.

Fig. 1. 2D visual tracking examples. Green box indicates the tracker output.

Perhaps one of the most successful family of tracking methodologies based on deep learning are those that employ Siamese architectures [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. They typically work by learning a template model from features describing the initial target region appearance in a reference region, and then cross-correlate it with regions in the succeeding frame. Deep learning-based trackers require a GPU to run in real-time in embedded system implementation.

Other successful 2D visual target tracking methods, employed in embedded systems are correlation filter based trackers [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. These methods, solve a ridge regression problem by learning a filter that regresses the target representations to a Gaussian distribution. The basic assumption is that the target to be detected in the next frame will be a translated version of the template model of the previous one. Exploiting the Fourier domain equivalence, correlation-filter methods are very fast and allow the tracking model updating in every consequent video frame. Despite their simplicity, they fail to achieve the performance of the more advanced deep-learning methods.

A state-of-the-art approach for 2D tracking in autonomous systems is to combine the advantages of both CNN-based architectures with the ones of correlation-filter based methods [16, 17]. Such methods introduce a deep-learning tracking architecture that is have been trained end-to-end and can exploit background information while being able to update the target model with new data online, in a similar fashion to

correlation-filter-based trackers. Nevertheless, we argue that the problem of online model updating has not been solved in an optimal fashion for deep-learning-based trackers, mostly due the complicated nature of deep neural network architectures.

In this paper, we propose a novel tracking model updating scheme for [16] inspired by Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) [18], that produces additional knowledge about the target distribution that otherwise are not be exploited by standard tracker updating schemes. We introduce a lightweight convolutional architecture that acts as a discriminator, assisting the online optimization of the tracking process. Our experimental results denote that our proposed updating scheme, increases the tracking precision of the baseline tracker in a well known 2D tracking benchmark, while maintaining the ability to perform real-time.

2. RELATED WORK

In recent years, deep Siamese architectures have been used successfully in order to perform real-time target tracking [1, 2, 3]. Although there are methods that utilize the background information and may prevent tracking failures due to distractors [4], the lack of an update mechanism in this category of trackers can become a major drawback, especially in long term tracking where the algorithm has to confront severe target appearance changes (e.g. change of view) or big occlusions.

Correlation filter based 2D visual tracking methods, can learn a tracking model and adapt it online to the target. Typically these methods form a vectorial representation \mathbf{x} of the target and construct a datamatrix \mathbf{X} that contains the input target template representations and all its cyclic shifts. By utilizing \mathbf{X} , a filter \mathbf{w} is trained in order to regress the data matrix \mathbf{X} to a Gaussian distribution \mathbf{y} with each peak corresponding to the untranslated vector \mathbf{x} while bigger translations of $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbf{X}$, are mapped to lower values. The tracking filter can be obtained fast in the Fourier domain:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}^* = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{x}}^* \odot \hat{\mathbf{y}}}{\hat{\mathbf{x}}^* \odot \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \lambda}, \quad (1)$$

and updated in every frame, after successful tracking, according to the new target appearance in the following frame:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}^* = (1 - h)\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{t-1}^* + h\hat{\mathbf{w}}_t^*, \quad (2)$$

where $0 < h \leq 1$ is the learning rate. Even if these methods adapt to the target, their performance is subpar to the Siamese methods.

In [16] and [17], a deep tracking architecture is proposed that unlike Siamese approaches can update the tracking model with new data online. This method employs a discriminative learning loss and an optimization strategy that ensures rapid convergence of the tracking model. The tracking model is in

fact the weights of a convolutional layer that provides target classification scores as output and is initialized by the target appearance.

The input to the model predictor consists of a training set \mathcal{S} of deep feature maps, which are generated from the backbone network. Each feature sample is paired with its ROI center coordinates $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The tracking model \mathbf{f} is a convolutional layer that aims in discriminating between the target and the background or distractors in the feature space. The loss utilized has the form of:

$$L(\mathbf{f}) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{S}_t|} \sum_{(x, \mathbf{c}) \in \mathcal{S}_t} \|r(\mathbf{X} * \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{c})\|^2 + \|\lambda \mathbf{f}\|^2, \quad (3)$$

where $*$ denotes convolution and λ is a regularization factor. The function $r(\mathbf{X} * \mathbf{f}, \mathbf{c})$ computes the residual at every spatial location based on the target scores and the ROI center coordinates \mathbf{c} . The filter is updated in the following manner:

$$\mathbf{f}^{(i+1)} = \mathbf{f}^{(i)} - a \nabla L(\mathbf{f}^{(i)}). \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{\nabla L(\mathbf{f}^{(i)})^T \nabla L(\mathbf{f}^{(i)})}{\nabla L(\mathbf{f}^{(i)})^T Q^{(i)} \nabla L(\mathbf{f}^{(i)})}. \quad (5)$$

These methods manage to outperform Siamese methods and correlation filter based methods.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

In this paper we propose a novel online tracking model update scheme inspired by GANs [18]. Typically, in GANs there are two sub-models, 1) the Generator model, G , that tries to generate new examples that could possibly belong to a training set of real data and the Discriminator D that tries to distinguish (classification task) the generated/fake ones produced by G and real data included in the training set. The aim of this training procedure is for G to manage to fool D , thus producing data that could possibly belong to the training set.

The tracking procedure may consist of a layer/filter with adjustable weights, which are initialized in the first frame and then can be updated online based on the new appearance of the target in the consecutive frames. This filter is applied to features describing the target appearance, producing Gaussian-like distributions. The proposed scheme considers this procedure as the fake data generation in a typical GAN. The proposed discriminator D , is a lightweight network, pre-trained offline on very few examples of the ideal distribution/output of the tracking procedure, which are considered to be the real data. The network consists of two convolutional layers followed by a fully connected layer. The output is a number between 0 and 1, with 1 indicating successful tracking and 0 otherwise. The architecture of the proposed network D is depicted in Figure 2.

In order to pre-train D we have obtained ideal responses of tracking model \mathbf{f} in terms of distribution. For instance,

Fig. 2. Discriminator architecture

the ideal distribution can be a Gaussian-like distribution Y_c , with its peak indicating the translation of the target, according to target center ROI location c . When the peak of Y_c is in the center, no translation has occurred and while the distance of the peak from the center increases so does the position of the target between two consecutive frames. In our training dataset we have included ideal distributions for all possible translations of the target.

The overall tracking architecture is depicted in Figure 3. Training set S_t is initialized by the first frame and data augmentation techniques, and is updated during the tracking process having a maximum capacity of 50 images. The optimization procedure, in order to train and update the discrimination model, utilizes image features extracted from a backbone network, given as input to the tracking layer/filter which produces the tracking scores.

Fig. 3. Tracking architecture

During inference, D is used to classify the produced distributions, thus producing loss that tries to steer the online trained tracking model to ignore peaks caused by distractors in the background. The calculated loss is in the form of:

$$L_D = -g_1 \log(o_1) - (1 - g_1) \log(1 - o_1) \quad (6)$$

where g is the groundtruth label and o the output score of the discriminator. Two losses are calculated for D . The first one L_{D_r} stems from the output of D when an ideal distribution is given as input and the second one L_{D_f} from the output of D when the tracking scores are given as input, thus the output of f when applied to the target features. In the first case D should classify the distributions as real data and the

second one as fake. The loss of tracking layer f is calculated using Eq. 6. Output is given by the updated D , although the groundtruth label in this case is the one corresponding to the real data. In order to optimize both D and f , ADAM optimizer [19] is utilized. The training/update procedure is described in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Discriminator D and tracking layer f weights update.

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1: procedure DISCRIMINATORUPDATE
2:    $o_1 \leftarrow$  ideal scores
3:    $D: \text{loss}(D(o_1), \text{True}).\text{backward}()$ 
4:    $o_2 \leftarrow \text{applyFilter}(f, \text{features})$ 
5:    $D: \text{loss}(D(o_2), \text{False}).\text{backward}()$ 
6:    $\text{Optimize}(D)$ 
7: procedure TRACKINGFILTERUPDATE
8:    $o \leftarrow \text{applyFilter}(f, \text{features})$ 
9:    $f: \text{loss}(D(o), \text{True}).\text{backward}()$ 
10:   $\text{Optimize}(f)$ 

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The proposed updating scheme in fact, penalizes peaks in the tracking scores caused by distractors forcing the weights of f to be updated in such a manner that these peaks will converge to zero values.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As a baseline tracking method we have employed DiMP [16] and PrDiMP [17]. Our tracking update scheme is implemented in Python using PyTorch. We evaluated the proposed scheme using ResNet-18 as the backbone network. The trackers with the proposed scheme are named **DiMP P** and **PrDiMP P** respectively and can achieve real-time performance on a single Nvidia GTX1080 GPU.

For the evaluation of the proposed framework, we utilized the videos from two publicly available video tracking benchmarks, namely **OTB100** [20] and **UAV123** [21]. Combined, they contain 223 fully annotated sequences in various scenes with challenging attributes for visual 2D target tracking such as occlusions, fast target and camera motion, background clutter etc.

In the experimental evaluation we exploit the one-pass evaluation (OPE) method. where the tracking algorithm is initialized in the first frame with the ground truth position and size of the object and tries to track the object for the rest of the video frames. Due to the stochastic nature of the baseline tracker each of the experiment is executed 5 times and the mean result is reported. Our evaluation is based on a widely used metric, namely Overlap Score (OS). Overlap Score defined as $S = \frac{|r_t \cap r_0|}{|r_t \cup r_0|}$, where r_t and r_0 is the tracked and ground truth bounding boxes respectively, \cap and \cup denote the intersection and union operators and $|\cdot|$ denotes the number of pixels inside the specified area. OS is calculated in

Fig. 4. Car tracking examples of OTB sequences. Green box indicates the tracking algorithm output.

Fig. 5. Success plot of OTB and UAV123.

a per frame basis. When the value of S is larger than a certain threshold (0.5 in our case), it is assumed that the tracker, successfully tracks the desired object.

Figure 5 depicts the success plots for both of the datasets used for evaluation. By examining the results, it should be noted that in both cases the methods that employ the proposed tracking update scheme outperform the baseline methods, by 1.0% both for DiMP and PrDiMP. **PrDiMP P** achieves the top performance overall compared to state-of-the-art trackers such as SiamRPN [3] and DaSiamRPN [4], while leaving far behind correlation filter based methods such as LDES-ODDA [12] which also implements a tracking failure detection and handling mechanism.

Table 1 depicts the FPS achieved for each method compared to the baseline one. By examining the results, we can determine that while when the proposed scheme is utilized there is a small decrease in FPS performance, the method still is able to perform real time. More specifically **PrDiMP P**

Table 1. FPS comparison between the tracking architectures with (bold) and without the proposed tracking update scheme in OTB100 and UAV123. Red values indicate top performance.

Tracker	PrDiMP P	PrDiMP	DiMP P	DiMP
FPS	35.94	37.09	39.03	41.32

has a mean average of 35.94 FPS in both datasets, achieving only about 1.5 FPS less than the baseline method. In the more lightweight **DiMP P**, the measured average FPS performance is equal to 39.03 being about 2 FPS slower than the baseline method.

In Figure 4 a qualitative evaluation of the proposed tracking framework is depicted in various car chasing scenarios. In the first two rows it can be noted that the tracker manages to track the correct vehicle in front of the car even if it the target is small. In the third sequence the tracker is producing boxes for a vehicle in front that changes lanes and in the last row there is severe motion blur in a lot of the frames, although the tracker manages to follow the car/target. The evaluation dataset includes more sequences similar to the ones depicted in Figure 4.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a novel 2D visual target tracking model update scheme has been described. This scheme allows the tracking model to learn the target distribution more efficiently, by adding a merely perceivable computational overload. This updating scheme is general and may be employed in other tracking architectures, without many changes to some baseline tracking algorithm. Our aim is to further improve the proposed tracking update scheme, by investigating various discriminator architectures and improved initialization/training techniques. Finally, the proposed tracking can be evaluated on embedded systems such as Nvidia Jetson.

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